

Sediment Yields Determination of Existing Bilibili Reservoir using Echosounder Data Analysis

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Abstract

This paper provides an overview of sediment yield analysis results using echosounder analysis to determine sediment amount in the Bilibili reservoir for current conditions. This study conducted in 2019 by conducting a direct survey by measuring using an echo sounder tool. With a topographic map (contour), the surface area at each elevation can be calculated with a Planimeter and then calculated the volume between the two elevations. Then it can be made surface area curve – elevation and storage volume curves – elevation. The result showed that the total volume of sediment in the Bilibili reservoir from 1997 to 2019 was 110.37 million m³, and measurements in 2017, the total volume of sediment was only 108.05 million m³. Therefore, the total sediment rate from 2017 to 2019 is 2.321 million m³. These results indicate a decrease in sediment amount over the past two years. The condition expected to continue so that the reservoir water level can be maintained. Calculations using echo sounder analysis show a significant accuracy level.

Keywords: Reservoir management, topographic map, echo sounder analysis, sediment yields.

1. Introduction

Capacities of reservoirs determined from a contour map with a particular scale (1: 10,000), and with an individual elevation difference (5-10 meters), more days will be further reduced due to the presence of sedimentation, and based on the report of Bili-Bili Multipurpose Dam Project, CTI Engineering Co. LTD in association with PT. Indra Karya and PT. Exsa International, in February 1988. Sediment transport for the Bilibili Dam planned at 1500 m³/km²/year, which is equivalent to the sedimentation rate of 1.5 mm/year. Total sediment volume over the life of the reservoir plan of 50 years is 29 million m³, the dead storage capacity of 12 million m³ at +65.00 elevation—data on the initial reservoir volume as the background condition as shown in Table 1. Based on the data shows that the sedimentation rate that occurred is quite large, coupled with the ridge collapse of Mount Bawakaraeng that occurred in 2004ech.

Furthermore, based on the current data, it is necessary to know the current sedimentation results as a basis for preventing potential flood disasters that can occur due to an increased water level elevation effect in increasing sediment yields. The study uses echosounder analysis to determine the current sediment yield of the Bilibili reservoir.

Several previous studies on reservoir sediment yield analysis and some problems using various methods in Indonesia have conducted and well reported. Comparative analysis of fluctuations in reservoir volume changes by the measurement method and water level elevation measurements [1]. Measurement for capacity evaluation of Ngancar Reservoir in Central Jawa using eco-sounder [2]. Reservoir water balance analysis between water availability and water requirements using Standard Operating Rule (SOR) method, and reservoir in-flow optimization was analyzed with NRECA model [3]. Based on the

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previous three studies concluded that eco-sounders analysis were significant accurate results. In addition, the studies of soil erosion and sediment fluxes analysis [4], spatial analysis to validated eco-sounder data of sediment fluxes and soil erosion [5]–[7].

Based on the previous studies, this study intends to find out how much the sediment transport of Bilibili reservoir at existing condition (2019) using eco-sounder analysis. The current sediment condition is important for reservoir management to prevent surface water level.

Table 1. Relationship of Reservoir Elevation, Area and Volume of Bilibili Reservoir in 2008

Elevation (m)	Area	Volume	Elevation (m)	Area	Volume
	km ²	million m ³		km ²	million m ³
50	0,000	0	75	4,979	33,318
54	0.339	0	80	7,304	61.28
56	0.487	0	85	9,803	98,364
58	0.759	0	90	12,844	149,043
60	1,062	0	95	15,104	217,131
62	1,401	0.518	99.5	17,412	287,641
64	1,803	1985	100	17,613	295,718
66	2,218	5,035	105	20,500	389,870
68	2,450	9,646	110	22,150	496,490
70	3,388	15,855			

2. Literature Review

Sedimentation can define as transportation, suspension, or deposition of all fragmental material by water [8], [9]. Sedimentation is a result of erosion and gives many impacts. In the river, bed sediment deposition causes the rise of the river bed, then causes high water levels so that it can result in floods that hit unprotected land [10], [11]. It also causes the flow to dry up and look for new grooves. In the channel, if the irrigation channel or shipping channel drained by water that is full of sediment, sediment deposition will occur at the bottom of the channel [12], [13]. Instead, a significant amount of money will require for dredging the sediment.

Moreover, in certain circumstances dredging sediment will cause the cessation of channel operation [14], [15]. In reservoirs, sediment deposition in reservoirs will reduce the effective volume of the reservoir. Most of the sediment flowed by the reservoir is sediment flowed by rivers flowing into the reservoir; only a small portion originates from avalanches of reservoir cliffs or originates from scours of reservoir cliffs by surface runoff [16]–[18]. Coarse grains will be deposited in the upper part of the reservoir while the little ones will deposit near the dam. So most of the sediment will be deposited in the active volume of the reservoir, and some can rinse down if there is a flood when the reservoir water level is still low [19]–[21]. In sluice gates, which cause difficulty in operating these gates. Also, because the formation of sand islands (*sand bars*) upstream of the dam or floodgates will disrupt the flow of water through the dam or floodgates, on the other hand, there will be a danger of scouring downstream of the building. If the sediment load in the river decreases due to deposition in the upper reaches of the dam, the flow can transport riverbed material. In areas along the river, as described above, flooding will occur more frequently in unprotected areas. The area protected by the dike will be safe, as long as the dike always elevated following the rise in the riverbed, and the water level will affect the drainage of the surrounding area. Over time drainage using gravity is no longer possible.

Water in-flow to the reservoir brings the erosion of sediment transport in the watershed, which then will partially settle in the reservoirs in the form of [22]–[24]: 1) *Wash load*, the sediment originates on the surface of the watershed. Mainly weathered by changes in temperature, transported by water in colloidal form, making it difficult to settle in reservoirs, flowing downstream with runoff water. 2) *Suspended load*, with coarser grains, about a few per hundred, s to several tens of millimeters, are transported in suspend/float into the reservoir. Most will be deposited downstream of the reservoir pond, along with a small portion of *the wash load*. 3) *Bedload* with grains that are coarser than suspended load, sliding, and rolling on the riverbed. Almost all of the bedload sediments will settle in the upstream reservoir ponds and at the bottom of the reservoir water supply reservoir.

3. Methodology of Research

This study conducted in 2019 by conducting a direct survey by measuring using an echo sounder tool. With a topographic map (contour), the surface area at each elevation can be calculated with a Planimeter and then calculated the volume between the two elevations. Then it can be made surface area curve – elevation and storage volume curves – elevation. The volume between two elevations can calculate using one of the following formulas.

$$V = \sum \frac{h}{2} (A_1 + A_2) = \left(\frac{A_1 + A_n}{2} + A_2 + A_3 + \dots + A_{n-1} \right) \dots \dots \text{(trapezoidal)} \dots \dots (1)$$

$$V = \sum \frac{h}{3} (A_1 + A_2 + \sqrt{A_1 A_2}) \dots \dots \dots \text{(cone)} \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

$$V = [(A_1 + A_n) + 4(A_2 + A_4 + \dots) + 2(A_3 + A_5 + \dots)] \dots \dots \text{(prismoidal)} \dots \dots (3)$$

Where: A_1, A_2, A_3, \dots etc. is the area between the elevation lines with different height h .

Reservoir capacity for various elevations of water level can be placed on an elevation-storage curve as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. The Relationship between Elevation, Area and Storage of Reservoir

This study was carried out with a series of measurements in the field that went through several stages, as seen in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Flow Chart of Study Stages

Before starting the field survey, equipment condition checks and determine the measurement points according to the BiliBili Reservoir contour map to fixed the survey location. Meanwhile, the measurement reference made the fixed point that already exists in the Bili-Bili Reservoir with a distance of 50 meters each. There are also methods of implementation of the study are: Measurement of baseline elevation of the reservoir with an *echosounder*. The principle measurement of *echosounder* is a *cross-section* measurement. Depth measurement is done by the ultrasonic wave reflection method which is emitted perpendicular to the surface of the water to the bottom by the *echosounder*, and then the wave will be reflected back.

The steps in making measurements with *echosounder* are as follows; a) determine the measurement points along with the distance of each point regarding existing points from previous measurements. b) installing *echosounder* on the boat. c) the *echosounder* operated on the boat, which moves slowly from the start to the end following the specified measurement path. Measurements made using the GARMIN *echosounder* type GPS-MAP 580/585 with a spacing between 50 m and a *Speedboat* speed of 5-10 km/h so that the resulting data is accurate; Zig-zag measurements were taken from point 1 to point 2 with a distance of 50 m, and proceed to the next point. From the results of measurements with *echosounder* data will be obtained, such as coordinate points, water depth, and water level. Basic mapping of reservoirs from *echosounder* measurements.

After obtaining the data from the measurement results with an *echosounder*, the next *step* is to make a base elevation map of the Bili-Bili reservoir following the measurement results—furthermore, the reservoir map *overlay* at the last measurement in 2017 and 2019. The *overlay* carried out to compare the elevation of the Bili-Bili Reservoir in the final measurement conditions with the elevation of the Bili-Bili Reservoir area that was made based on the results of measurements with *echosounder* in conditions s this time. This comparison used to overview sediment volume in the current condition is due to the sediment change of the Bili-Bili Reservoir.

Longitudinal and transverse cuts are making in reservoir areas. Furthermore, conducted based on the results of the overlaying reservoir in the last measurement in 2017 with reservoir contour areas in 2019 measurements. Making longitudinal cuts aims to see the sediment distribution in the Bilibili reservoir, Gowa Regency. While making cross-section aims to see how extensive the sediment is in the Bili-Bili reservoir, Gowa Regency.

The calculation sediment area was done by calculation at each cross-section. The cross-section did after mapping the reservoir base measurement results with *echosounder* that has been overlaid with mapping the results of previous measurements. The final results of this study are in the form of a contour elevation map of the Bili-Bili Reservoir under current conditions (2019) and regarding the total sediment volume and increase from 2017 to 2019 in the Bili-Bili Reservoir, Gowa Regency.

4. Results and Discussion

Echosounder measurements in 2019 produce an overview reservoir bathymetry map, as shown in Figure 3. Based on the map data, the distance and elevation data used to determine area and volume. Furthermore, to calculate the subsurface area and volume, the area between the two elevations is calculated using a Planimeter, and the volume is determined. The total volume calculated using equations 1, 2, and 3.

Figure 3. Bed Level of Bilibili Reservoir Result of Echosounder Measurement in 2019

Furthermore, subsurface reservoir conditions in 2017 and 2019 are overlaid and produce a contour map, as shown in Figure 4. Based on this overlay data, the condition of sediment yields for the last two years has determined.

Figurer 4. Overlay Result of Contour Area Map in 2017 and 2019

Meanwhile, the description of the reservoir sub-surface elevation since 1997, 2017, and 2019 shown as in Figure 5 and indicated that bed elevation increase caused by the transport of sediment going through the reservoir as a result of the heavy rain in raining season. However, in this survey the increasing not significant, as the measurement not covered all the area.

Figure 5. Graph of bed elevation in 1997 until 2019

Based on Figure 5, the increase in bed surface elevation between 1997-2017 was significant at distances less than 5000 m, indicating a significant increase in sediment volume. While between 2017-2019, the difference in bed surface elevation was not significant, indicating that the difference in sediment volume was not significant.

Based on the results of research and calculations, the total volume of sediment in the Bilibili reservoir from 1997 to 2019 was 110.37 million m³, and in measurements in 2017, the total volume of sediment was only 108.05 million m³. Therefore, the total sediment rate from 2017 to 2019 is 2.321 million m³. These results indicate a decrease in sediment amount over the past two years. The condition expected to continue so that the reservoir water level can be maintained.

5. Conclusion

Sediment yields analysis using echosounder on the Bilibili reservoir was conducted and concluded that there was a decrease in sediment amount for two years (2017-2019) of 2,321 million m³. These results indicate that sediment management in the Bilibili reservoir is proper. Calculations using echosounder analysis show a significant degree of accuracy.

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